

QUIZ

LAST NAME: DOSHI

FIRST NAME: NAMRATA

PROGRAM CODE: DSDD

COURSE CODE : ACA 401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2007 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMARY OF ACA 401D

1. **While writing for the European Commission, which is the correct form for writing ‘organization?’**
 - Organization.
 - Organisation.**¹
 - Both.
 - None of the above.

2. **Using your own words and phrasing to replace most words mean which of the following methods of mentioning what you read?**
 - Summarizing.
 - Quoting.
 - Highlight.

¹ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Eighth Edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 32.

Paraphrase.²

3. **Which of the following is a part of a well thought out proposal (all or more than one can be correct)?**

Problem statement.

Purpose statement.

Data collection.

All of the above.³

4. **When a fact is repeated in many sources, it is safe to assume it is common knowledge even if the researcher is not aware of it. How does that impact citations?**

Mention it in references.

There is no need to cite it.⁴

Include it in footnotes.

Make it a part of your bibliography.

5. **Define winnowing process.**

To make data organized into sections.

² European Commission, *English Style Guide : A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Seventh Edition (European Commission, 2011), 51.

³ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications Inc., 2008), 17–18.

⁴ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 10.

- To structure the data into tables.
 - To reduce all data collected into manageable database.**⁵
 - To edit the database.
6. **The name ‘European Community’ is now replaced with what new version?**
- European Union.
 - EU.
 - European Union or EU, European Community can be used for historical references.**⁶
 - European Union or EU.
7. **A logical connection between data-collection methods chosen, research questions, and research approach is required for which part of your dissertation?**
- Literature Review.
 - Data Collection.
 - Presenting Methodology and Research Approach.**⁷
 - Organizing your Data.
8. **Choose an option with correct choice of literature.**
- The team lost its momentum.**⁸

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 102.

⁶ European Commission, *English Style Guide*, 51.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 73.

- The client expressed its too late to consider changes.
- The baby held on to it's toy.
- The local residents understand its critical to ensure safety.

9. **Which of the following does not apply to writing the methodology chapter?**

- Question.
- Purpose.
- Solution.**⁹
- Problem.

10. **Choose the incorrect option.**

- Tom and I went to see the movie.
- The teacher advised the student to go with John and him.
- I and him are best friends.**¹⁰
- Lucy and I enjoy biking.

⁸ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*, 18.

⁹ Philip Adu, "Writing the Methodology Chapter of Qualitative Study - EUCLID University ACA 401 and ACA 401-D," LMS at EUCLID University, accessed August 8, 2020, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-4/>.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*, 23.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Adu, Philip. "Writing the Methodology Chapter of Qualitative Study - EUCLID University ACA 401 and ACA 401-D." LMS at EUCLID University. Accessed August 8, 2020. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-4/>.
- Bloomberg, Linda, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications Inc., 2008.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
- European Commission. *English Style Guide : A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Seventh Edition. European Commission, 2011.
- Turabian, Kate. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Eighth Edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.